

Owen Barfield's Anthroposophical Anthropology: Humanity Received and Recapitulating

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Now they know that everything you have given me is from you, for the words that you gave to me I have given to them, and they have received them and know in truth that I came from you, and they have believed that you sent me.

Jn 17:7-8 (NRSV)

Introduction

In the face of contemporary societal and individual fragmentation of meaning, coupled with a paradoxical widespread personal disconnection in the age of technological or virtual connection, Owen Barfield's (1898–1997) philosophy offers compelling food for thought to 21st-century spirituality. This article attempts to explore Barfield's anthroposophical anthropology and highlight similarities with more traditional Christian anthropology. It will be observed that core Christian beliefs resonate more closely with Barfield's centrality of Spirit, which for him is historically manifested in the evolution of consciousness, than with secular anthropology. Barfield does not merely bypass secular philosophy to return to an outmoded way of thinking, but critiques such philosophy to transcend it with a hope-imbued and future-oriented one. Barfield's thought, thus, could offer a bridge to engage with spiritual seekers in the post-traditional time, when much of the traditional religious language appears alien to them.

Owen Barfield's Anthroposophical Anthropology

Much of Barfield's philosophy is an elaboration of thoughts already present in Rudolf Steiner's teachings. The most central idea in Barfield's thought is the evolution of consciousness, a concept also central to anthroposophy. However, this is not to say that Barfield simply recycled Steiner. Barfield's initial intuition was wholly original and related to the origin and development of language. As he elaborated on this intuition, he discovered that Steiner had already expounded on many of the emerging themes to a high degree. As he matured as a scholar, Barfield adopted core insights from anthroposophy and elaborated them in the context of language, poetry and philosophy. Barfield's literary and philosophical approach complemented and extended Steiner's teachings.

Barfield distinguishes between consciousness, which is whole and cosmic, and self-consciousness, which is part of the whole and individual. Self-consciousness arises from consciousness and never stops being part of it. This development of self-consciousness is part of the evolution of consciousness, which is still ongoing and moving towards a new wholeness. Barfield's originality with respect to Steiner is that his point of departure is an observation he makes in the development of language and meaning.

In one of his earlier texts, *Poetic Diction: A Study in Meaning*, Barfield observes that the initial development of language was on the other side of the same coin as the development of self-consciousness. Initially, words referred to objects, but objects signified more than their concrete physical aspect. As language developed, these single meanings split into pairs: "the abstract and the concrete, particular and general, objective and subjective."¹ Barfield gives the example of the verb "to shine," which at one point split into the meaning of physical light and the meaning of human thought. Originally, these two meanings were one meaning with two aspects, the spiritual (which gave rise to "thought") and the material (which gave rise to "physical light").² Nowadays, when brought together, these two meanings produce a metaphor.³ Thus, Barfield says that originally, the meaning was pictorial because it was unitary. For Barfield, the early human being was imbued with natural meaning. Moreover, this was how, according to Barfield, myth arose: not because a particular storyteller, or group of storytellers, decided to invent a story about gods, but because people

1 Owen Barfield, *Poetic Diction: A Study in Meaning*, 4th ed. (Oxford: Barfield Press, 2010), 78.

2 Ibid., 81.

3 Ibid., 80.

of antiquity actually *perceived* the gods according to their consciousness and the development stage of language. A myth was “not an abstract conception, but the echoing footsteps of the goddess Natura – not a metaphor but a living Figure.”⁴

A significant implication of this theory on the rise of myth with language and meaning development is that people did not always think in the way we do today. It is not that they thought different things, but they thought differently. While, for example, we might feel a breeze in our face and let it remind us of the quiet presence of God, for the people of antiquity, a breeze *was* God’s presence.⁵ This change in perception aligns with anthroposophical anthropology, which views the human being as being in a continuous process of becoming. In turn, this implies that human consciousness did not suddenly appear out of nothing, or out of a particular genetic mutation in an ape-like creature. Nor was consciousness immediately as it is today, lacking only the sophisticated language and abstract thought of today. Rather, at one point in the universe’s history, according to Barfield, a cosmic pre-human consciousness dressed itself in human form, and the resulting self-consciousness continued to develop in this new form. “It was not man who made the myths but the myths, or the archetypal substance they reveal, which made man.”⁶ In an essay, Barfield likens the emerging humanity to a wind-harp that is played by the passing air. While our present consciousness is such that it resembles a camera obscura, which has an inside that receives stimuli from outside and responds to them, original self-consciousness was more like a wind-harp: “The wind-harp becomes what it is by itself becoming an ‘inside’ for the enviroing air, by becoming a modulated voice for it to speak with.”⁷ In this way, self-consciousness emerged out of an “antecedent wholeness,” initially expressed itself in myths and symbols, and eventually in more abstract language and thoughts. Mythology transformed into philosophy, together with a sense of moral agency, while humanity

4 Ibid., 81.

5 Elsewhere, Barfield wrote: “[T]he thoughts themselves were images rather than concepts. And this entails that the world they lived in was different from the world we live in today. It would be as true, perhaps truer, to say that they *perceived* images as to say that they thought them. What we perceive as things they perceived as images [...] The difference between an image and a thing lies in the fact that an image presents itself as an exterior expressing or implying an interior, whereas a thing does not” (Owen Barfield, *History, Guilt and Habit*, 2nd ed. (Oxford: Barfield Press, 2012), 47).

6 Owen Barfield, “The Harp and the Camera,” in *The Rediscovery of Meaning and Other Essays*, 2nd ed. (Oxford: Barfield Press, 2013), 110.

7 Ibid., 105.

gradually lost access to an immediate supernatural meaning. Barfield criticises modern anthropology and psychology for projecting onto “primitive man” our modern consciousness.

I am firmly persuaded that we shall never get anywhere with our anthropological attempts at reconstructing the mind of primitive man until we make up our minds to throw away all this projection business. If we *must* think in metaphor (and we must), why not try beginning again on the assumption that primitive man was not a camera obscura but an aeolian harp? Surely it is only by this route that we can hope to understand the origin of myths and of thinking at all.⁸

Barfield also criticises modernity for first doing away with the idea of spirit, or the accessibility to it, and then coming up with the idea of the unconscious to substitute the original link with nature while keeping humanity separate from it.

Apart from a certain number of hard-boiled empiricists and behaviourists, most people today concede to the psyche that “inwardness” which they deny to nature, and they call it the unconscious mind — or the unconscious. (...) We must not speak of any mind or intelligence *in* nature — because it is taboo. Might it not make things less complicated if we were now to infringe the taboo and concede that what we call unconscious, or unself-conscious, mind is in fact the inwardness of nature as well as of ourselves? (...) (*quoting Coleridge*) “The intelligence, which is in the human mind above nature,” is of course the conscious mind, and the unconscious mind, which is also “the productive power in nature,” is one kind with it.⁹

In a different text, Barfield wrote more concisely and more clearly:

Consciousness is not a tiny bit of the world stuck onto the rest of it. It is the inside of the whole world; or, if we are using the term in its

8 Ibid., 109.

9 Owen Barfield, “Science and Quality,” in *The Rediscovery of Meaning and Other Essays*, 2nd edition (Oxford: Barfield Press, 2013), 268.

stricter sense, excluding therefore the subconscious mind, then it is *part* of the inside of the whole world.¹⁰

Barfield, therefore, presents humanity as that part of the world where consciousness is manifested most. At this point, it is essential to note that Barfield does not confuse consciousness with God. Raised in an agnostic household, as an adult, Barfield came to the faith in Christ mainly through his intellectual engagement with philology.¹¹ As a Christian, but already earlier as an anthroposophist, Barfield believed that God, who is unchanging Objective Reality and the source and ground of all, created Consciousness, which is evolving and is subjective experience. God is transcendent, yet immanent in creation. Barfield does not consider Creation as a one-time material event only, but mainly as a process of unfolding meaning. As human meaning is linked intimately to language, it is unsurprising that Barfield's contribution to anthroposophical thought was related mainly to the linguistic role. Just as language developed alongside the evolution of consciousness, becoming the means by which humans co-create reality, Creation is, at its basis, linguistic, in that God speaks it into being. God's Logos, thus, permeates creation. While the Logos remains one and the same throughout history, creation changes with the evolution of consciousness, the latter being the "inwardness" of the created world and culminating in human self-consciousness.

Barfield refers to Aquinas's Trinitarian theology, saying that the Divine Word proceeds from the Father but does not leave Him. The Divine Logos permeates Creation while remaining with God. This is analogous to what happens with human words when they are spoken: the meaning reaches the listener without leaving the speaker.¹² Barfield explains that the difference between the Divine Word and human words, that is, between the Logos and the human logos, lies in that the human word relies for its origin on the memory. It has to crystallize,

10 Barfield, *History, Guilt and Habit*, 11.

11 In his essay "Philology and the Incarnation," Barfield maintains that a historical study of language development and semantic change reveals that at the time of the Incarnation of Christ, texts indicate a clear paradigm shift in language use, which in turn indicates a shift in consciousness. See Owen Barfield, "Philology and the Incarnation," in *The Rediscovery of Meaning and Other Essays*, 2nd ed. (Oxford: Barfield Press, 2013), 338–350.

12 See Owen Barfield, "Meaning, Revelation and Tradition in Language and Religion," *The Missouri Review*, 5, no. 3 (Summer 1982): 121–122. At the beginning of this essay, Barfield claims that all he ever wrote on language was somehow an attempt to discover the link between words and their history, and "the Word" mentioned in Jn 1:1.

so to speak, around some grain of sense perception given from outside itself and retained in itself. Whereas the Divine Word is self-generating. What the memory is to the human word the Creator himself, God the Father, is to the Divine Word.¹³

Barfield argues that words are primary symbols that, rather than relating to their object in terms of likeness, do so in terms of revelation. Words reveal the meaning of an otherwise unmanifestable reality. Moreover, if words are not considered as primary symbols of consciousness, language cannot be apprehended as meaning. “Meaning, as distinct from mere information, always has an element of revelation in it.”¹⁴ For Barfield, then, human words manifesting consciousness are essential links between the Divine Word and the rest of Creation. He maintains that if one were to insist on thinking in terms of likeness, one must think of a “kind of likeness that may subsist between the generated and the generant, to conceive of the manifest being in some manner the ‘image’ of the unmanifest.”¹⁵ Thus, words do not just reveal the meaning of their object, but are also the material means of revelation of the supernatural and the greater Reality. This brings us back to the coeval development of language and myth at the dawn of self-consciousness that Barfield writes of in *Poetic Diction*. These notions throw a different light onto the ecclesial notion of the *semina verbi*. Furthermore, Barfield distinguishes between the archetype and the signature elements in myths. In brief, the archetype is what comes from the Divine Logos through consciousness, while the signature is the work of an individual mind that puts the myth into writing.¹⁶

13 Ibid., 124–125. The reference to the Father indicates that the “self” of “Self-generating” refers to the Trinity as one, rather than to the Word as the Second Person of the Trinity. About the generation of human words, in an earlier text, Barfield writes: “When a word is formed or spoken, the original unity of the ‘inner’ word is polarized into a duality of outer and inner, that is, of sound and meaning; so, when man himself was ‘uttered,’ that is, created, the cosmic wisdom became polarized, in and through him, into a duality of appearance and intelligence, representation and consciousness. But when creation has become polarised into consciousness on the one side and phenomena, or appearances, on the other, memory is made possible, and begins to play an all-important part in the process of evolution. For by means of his memory man makes the outward appearances an inward experience. He acquires his self-consciousness from them. When I experience the phenomena in memory, I make them ‘mine,’ not now by virtue of any original participation, by my own inner activity.” Owen Barfield, *Saving the Appearances: A Study in Idolatry*, 3rd ed. (Oxford: Barfield Press, 2011), 181–182.

14 Barfield, “Meaning, Revelation and Tradition,” 124.

15 Ibid., 122.

16 Barfield, “The Harp and the Camera,” 109–110.

In the evolution of consciousness, Christ, the Incarnation of the unique Divine Word, takes a determining role, confirming that despite the enormous part taken by the evolution of consciousness in the unfolding of creation, Barfield's framework is not based on deism but on a clear Christian theism. At the same time, it needs to be acknowledged that the centrality of Christ is also present in Steiner's anthroposophy.

In *Saving the Appearances*, Barfield writes at length about the process from a generalised consciousness, which included both humanity and nature, and which he calls original participation, to an individualised and cut-off self-consciousness. In *Romanticism Comes of Age*, Barfield referred to this alienated self-consciousness through an anthroposophical term: the Consciousness Soul. Barfield maintained that in original participation, humans unconsciously identified with their Creator and with nature, but this identification shrank as self-consciousness increased with the origin and development of language. Vestiges of this original participation remained up till the late Middle Ages and the start of modernity. The Consciousness Soul has, however, reached a stage far beyond the healthy value of the individual person. Barfield attributes the increase in mental health problems (already in the 1970s at least) to this stage of the individualised self-consciousness and the pervasive sense of "cut-offness" and meaninglessness while remaining in reality united to the "original source in the spirit."¹⁷ Yet, one of the elements that still makes Barfield's philosophy attractive to Christians in the 21st century, when the sense of individualism has not abated, is that it still offers hope. The Incarnation of Christ made it possible for an unprecedented further transformation to take place in the evolution of consciousness. "Unprecedented" because it is not a matter of returning to original participation, but of evolving into final participation. Neither is it possible to return to accessing meaning in nature in the immediate way of our ancestors from thousands of years ago. Meaning (which, for Barfield, is generated by metaphor, which in turn for Barfield is more than a literary device), nowadays, needs to be recovered, and the Incarnation made this possible. Barfield maintains that if the Divine Word clothed itself with humanity, the Creator can now speak through humanity. While original participation was unaware of itself, final participation will involve the human will. The Incarnation was a perfecting of the human will, and the Consciousness Soul, then, was not

17 See Owen Barfield, *History, Guilt and Habit*, 34–35.

an unmitigated evil, but a necessary part of the evolution of consciousness to make possible a wilful response to the Creator by humanity. Barfield writes:

What in fact happened according to the record? In the heart of that nation, whose whole impulse it had been to eliminate original participation, a man was born who simultaneously identified himself with, and carefully distinguished himself from, the Creator of the world – whom he called the Father. On the one hand: “I am not alone, but I and the Father that sent me,” etc. On the other: “I and the Father are one,” etc. In one man the inwardness of the Divine Name had been fully realised; the final participation, whereby man’s Creator speaks from within man himself, had been accomplished. The Word had been made flesh.¹⁸

From a linguistic perspective, while, as was seen earlier, in original participation, there were no metaphors but figurative unitary meanings, once self-consciousness has advanced, the construction of metaphor through the unitive force of the imagination became possible and even necessary for meaning. For Barfield, the Incarnation was the moment in history when the evolution of consciousness turned its direction: words and language indicated a cessation of original participation (leaving only vestiges) and started showing signs of final participation. For Barfield, the Eucharist is, in fact, a symbol of this already-and-not-yet of final participation.¹⁹

Barfield claims that philologists assert that words appear as fossilised metaphors if one looks into their history. Ancient words and languages, thus, no longer offer meaning but only “husks of meaning.”²⁰ The same applies to

18 Barfield, *Saving the Appearances*, 199.

19 It is noteworthy that anthroposophists, too, venerate the Eucharist, albeit with varying nuances to Christian beliefs of more traditional denominations. Barfield writes: “The tender shoot of final participation has from the first been acknowledged and protected by the Church in the institution of the Eucharist. For all who partake of the Eucharist first acknowledge that the man who was born in Bethlehem was ‘of one substance with the Father,’ and that ‘all things were made’ by him; and then they take that substance into themselves, together with its representations named bread and wine. This is after all the heart of the matter. There was no difficulty in understanding it, as long as enough of the old participating consciousness survived. It was only as this faded, it was only as a ‘substance’ behind the appearances gradually ceased to be an experience and dimmed to a hypothesis or a credo, that the difficulties and doctrinal disputes concerning trans-substantiation began to grow” (Barfield, *Saving the Appearances*, 200).

20 Barfield, “Meaning, Revelation and Tradition,” 124.

words and languages that are still in use today but which have a long history. By the term “husks of meaning,” Barfield means that meaning no longer has an effective force on our lives; it only remains cognitive. The remedy for this loss of meaning and to revivify the fossilised metaphors lies in “the *act* of using language and the *faculty* of apprehending it as a tissue of symbols.”²¹ He continues,

In the case of religion, it is in much the same way – and, indeed, it is in close association with that very process of sedimentation – that what began as revelation fades into tradition. And here again, the only known remedy for sedimentation appears to be the way of symbol. For tradition to re-acquire the pristine energy, so to speak, of revelation, it needs to be apprehended not *only* as historical record by *also* as a symbol.²²

Here, Barfield seems to be synthesising the Catholic belief in the Eucharist at the roots of anthroposophy and that of High Anglicanism in which he was baptised. In any case, at the core is the importance of the imagination, which can see once again the original unitary figures of meaning.²³ The imagination is, therefore, critical for final participation. The imagination allows us to write myths once again with the same power to form lives as the old myths of original participation had.

(T)he ultimate question, to which imagination holds the key, is the question, of how we can learn to sign our own names to what we create, whether as myth or in other ways, but so nevertheless that what we sign as our own will also be the name of Another – the name

21 Ibid.

22 Ibid.

23 Similarly to the previous quote, in *Poetic Diction* from many years earlier, Barfield writes: “The language of primitive men reports them as direct perceptual experience. The speaker has observed a unity, and is not therefore himself conscious of *relation*. But we, in the development of consciousness, have lost the power to see this one as one. Our sophistication, like Odin’s, has cost us an eye; and now it is in the language of poets, in so far as they create true metaphors, which must *restore* this unity conceptually, after it has been lost from perception. Thus, the ‘before-unapprehended’ relationships of which Shelley spoke, are in a sense ‘forgotten’ relationship. For though they were never yet apprehended, they were at one time seen. And imagination can see them again” (Barfield, *Poetic Diction*, 79).

I would venture to say, without venturing to pronounce it, of the Author and the Lord of the archetypes themselves.²⁴

At a practical level, the use of the imagination in view of final participation has a concrete outcome, which, however, is quite difficult to achieve: breaking free from the *collective* mental habit of modern self-consciousness. Barfield makes it clear that this is not about philosophising. The imprisonment of the Consciousness Soul is found in our instruments of thought and perception, in the meanings of the most common words in use. Barfield says that this mental habit is so ingrained that it is popularly known as “common sense,” which in turn is dictated by “causality-science.”

There are different consequences associated with this breakout from collective mental habits. One of the more important ones is the strengthening of the imagination. Barfield cites Coleridge in saying that “imagination is really thinking with a bit of will in it.”²⁵ Imagination, here, has little to do with fantasy as it is popularly thought, but refers to the ability to engage more fully with reality. This is not a positivist engagement, but one that resorts to the depths of spirit and meaning, the inwardness of reality that Barfield stresses so much. This is why it is a fuller engagement than classical science can offer on its own. Di Fuccia, drawing from several of Barfield’s texts, sums up the role of the imagination thus:

It is the imagination that drinks from the primal source of meaning (the *logos*) when actively participating in God’s creative activity. It is the creative imagination that assists in crafting forms in nature, as humans “half perceive” and “half create” using the imagination.²⁶

Therefore, in practice, it is the imagination that, in the unfolding of Creation, is the motor of the evolution of consciousness. However, the imagination, as hinted at already through the reference to Coleridge’s definition, has to do with the individual’s will. This, in turn, points to something that is easily missed among all the parts of the entirety of Barfield’s philosophical framework: the individual’s personal value. Even though the mental habits that need to be

24 Barfield, “The Harp and the Camera,” 114.

25 Barfield, *History, Guilt and Habit*, 54.

26 Michael Vincent Di Fuccia, *Owen Barfield: Philosophy, Poetry, and Theology* (Eugene, OR: Cascade Books, 2016), 200.

broken for final participation to be possible are collective, Barfield says that the effort needs to start with the individual will, which then sums up with that of other individuals.²⁷ In the context of the Nazi totalitarian threat to freedom in 1940, Barfield wrote in an article: “We should see that man must be free, not because he is a trader, but because he is a spirit; he must be an individual because God speaks to and through the individual, and for no other reason.”²⁸

Conclusion: Humanity Received and Recapitulating

The anthropology that is gleaned from Barfield’s framework is one that is similar to that found in Christianity. In fact, Barfield was not only an anthroposophist but also a convinced Anglican. The human, in a generic way, is a creature that has been, and still is, in a process of evolution. As such, it is more correct to speak of a “human becoming” rather than “human being.” This “becoming,” however, is linked intimately to the rest of creation as its “inwardness.”

The evolution of nature and the evolution of consciousness cannot be separated, but have amounted together to what I will venture to call “the evolution of anthropocentricity.” And that is of course very different from the evolution that was assumed by Darwinians (...) For we have to assume, if we adopt it, not that man, after having been for a long time nonexistent, eventually emerged as one of the higher animals, but rather that anthropos was present from the beginning, though without the “centric” consciousness which we experience today focused clearly and sharply into body and brain.²⁹

Moreover, this “becoming” is teleologically guided by the Divine Logos that manifests itself primarily in the human logos, and reached the apex of such manifestation in the Incarnation of Christ. In this sense, then, Barfield’s anthropology shows humanity as being “received” by humans from a cosmic and generic pre-human consciousness, simultaneously as “recapitulating” the unfolding creative process of the Divine Word.

27 Barfield, *History, Guilt and Habit*, 54–55.

28 Owen Barfield, “An Effective Approach to Social Change,” *The Christian News-Letter* Supplement to 39 (July 24, 1940), unpaginated, quoted in Jeffrey Hipolito, *Owen Barfield’s Poetic Philosophy: Meaning and Imagination* (London: Bloomsbury, 2024), 143.

29 Barfield, “Science and Quality,” 266.

Given the scenario where Christian spirituality is one option among many,³⁰ any pastoral action that does not seek to be a monologue or merely a “sermon to the converted” needs to start from anthropology. A theology that believes in the endurance of the Incarnation cannot avoid examining the symbols that thrive in contemporary society. In the post-traditional, succumbing to the temptation of seeking the truth in *exclusively* familiar circles, no matter how reliable and embedded in tradition they are, betrays the *tradition* itself. This “anthropological urgency” has already been noted in 20th-century theology, and the emergence of spirituality as a discipline from Christian circles attests to it, in that Christians came to realise that spirituality in the world extends beyond their theological parameters. Still, Barfield remains relevant today because human consciousness is still undergoing further individualisation.

Whether one agrees with his conclusions or not, Barfield remains an example of someone who arrived to faith in Christ via a non-traditional path. Barfield was as interested in the ultimate truth as any Christian apologist, despite taking a different path, as life provided him with. For Barfield, the ultimate truth was the point of arrival through life’s discoveries. His path could be labelled an anthropological path, not least because anthroposophy highlighted for him the humanity in theology.

Barfield claimed that primordial humanity was formed by myths that arose simultaneously with self-consciousness. The Logos is still present in creation today despite modern self-consciousness’s unawareness of it. Contemporary myths will still arise today with the potency to shape humanity. The difference is that they will require individuals’ attention for this potency to be actualised.

In the post-secular and post-traditional, when objectivity is simultaneously challenged by the humanities and sought by science, Barfield’s path is significant. He writes that there are two mental habits that need to be broken in this regard:

the “non-objectifying” subjectivity, in which the humanities are immured, and the adjoining cell of subjectless objectivity, where science is locked and bolted; and maybe the first step toward escape

30 See, for example, Charles Taylor, *A Secular Age* (Cambridge, MA: Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2007).

for the two prisoners of language is to establish communications with one another.³¹

This significance is also there in the context of a plurality of imported spiritualities, which promise to be more experiential than conceptual. Traditional religions, including Christianity, are undoubtedly experiential, but there is no denying that at times they feel sedimented, depleted of energy and reduced to concepts. Today more than ever, spirituality and its study need to tread the path of subjectivity and the subjective will to arrive at the objective Truth, which, in turn, cannot but integrate the Subject and the subject. In this way, Truth, like Barfield's notion of humanity, is received and recapitulated.

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³¹ Barfield, "Language and Discovery," in *The Rediscovery of Meaning and Other Essays*, 2nd ed. (Oxford: Barfield Press, 2013), 205.